

Fermat's Last Theorem:

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

additional proof(v4)

Therefore $(Z - X)$ must be n -th power.

$$Z - X = R^n$$

By same logic about $(Z - Y)$,

$$Z - Y \neq p$$

$$Z - Y \neq p^2$$

$$Z - Y = p_1^n \times p_2^n \times \cdots \times p_k^n$$

$$\therefore Z - Y = L^n$$

Therefore $(Z - Y)$ must also be a n -th power.

But $L = R = 1$ is impossible. Because it means that

$$X = Z - R^n = Z - 1$$

$$Y = Z - L^n = Z - 1$$

$$(Z - 1)^n + (Z - 1)^n = Z^n$$

$$2(Z - 1)^n = Z^n$$

$$2 = \frac{Z^n}{(Z - 1)^n}$$

2 is not a n -th power. So it is contradiction and it is impossible.

Therefore at least one of R and L is a natural number greater than or equal to 2.

i) $(Z - X) = R^n$ (n -th power)

ii) $(Z - Y) = L^n$ (n -th power)

Therefore the following two forms are that (X, Y, Z) must be satisfied at the same time.

i) $(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$

ii) $(X, Y, Z) = (LB, Z - L^n, Z)$

i) $(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$

$\gcd(R, A) = 1$. Because if not, $\gcd(R, A) = g \geq 2$,

Y^n is a multiple of g^{2n} .

$$(Z - R^n)^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

If we expand, Z^n on both sides are canceled and

$$\left\{ -\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} R^n + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} (R^n)^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 (R^n)^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z (R^n)^{n-1} - R^n \right\} + Y^n = 0$$

all terms except $-\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} R^n$ are multiples of g^{2n} .

$\gcd(g, n) = 1$. If not, Y is a multiple of n , which is contradiction.

$\gcd(g, Z^{n-1}) = 1$. If not, Z and $Y = RA$ have a common divisor g .

ii)

The same logic applies to ii).

$$\gcd(L, B) = 1$$

$$\gcd(L, Z) = 1$$

$$\gcd(B, Z) = 1$$

i) $(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$

ii) $(X, Y, Z) = (LB, Z - L^n, Z)$

i) and ii) must be satisfied at the same time.

Therefore, we also get

$$iii) (X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, Z - L^n, Z)$$

$$iv) (X, Y, Z) = (LB, RA, Z)$$

Just choose what you need and use it.

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$Y^n = Z^n - X^n = (Z - X) \times \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

$$\frac{Y^n}{Z - X} = \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

Let's choose ii).

$$\text{ii) } (X, Y, Z) = (LB, Z - L^n, Z)$$

$$\frac{Y^n}{Z - X} = \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

Let's substitute $X = LB$ and $Y = Z - L^n$.

$$\frac{Z - L^n}{Z - LB} = \Phi_n(Z, X) = (\textit{natural number})$$

Therefore $(Z - L^n)$ must be a multiple of $(Z - LB)$.

Therefore $(Z - L^n)$ must have $(Z - LB)$ as a factor.

If we substitute $Z = LB$, the value of $(Z - LB)$ and $(Z - L^n)$ be 0 at the same time.

$$LB - L^n = 0$$

$$\therefore B = L^{n-1}$$

B is a multiple of L , which is contradiction.

Therefore the ordered pair we obtained is impossible.

Same logic is possible with Y is a multiple of n . I already derived that $Z - Y = A^n$, if the Y is a multiple of n .

Therefore Fermat's last theorem is true.

Thank you for reading.